

Framework for Circularity and Efficiency Assessment and Optimisation of Symbiotic Circular Economy Solutions

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ABSTRACT

Water-related symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) seek to recover resources from the water cycle to reduce waste and our dependence on virgin resources. This attempt to move towards the circular economy should be accompanied by a comprehensive assessment framework. This report presents such a framework comprised of methods of assessment and optimisation, along with application examples. The material circularity indicator (MCI) method makes use of annual flows of material, energy, and financial resources to generate an indicator that lies between 0 (linear) and 1 (circular), representing how circular an SCES is. Next, a set of efficiency indicators are introduced based on different cost and benefit indicators. The costs may be expressed as resources used or their environmental impacts. The benefits may be expressed as recovered resources or in terms of the service unit of a process. For optimisation, compromise programming MCDA is discussed that allows a user to compare alternative SCES on different criteria and using different perspectives. Furthermore, an optimisation approach is discussed focusing on circularity and resource efficiency in a value chain context. Overall, this framework can be applied to assess and optimise SCES based on several efficiency and circularity indicators.

KEYWORDS

Symbiotic circular economy solutions, Circularity, Efficiency, Resource recovery, Water, MCDA, Optimisation, Value chain

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Executive summary

The report presents a detailed description of a circularity and efficiency assessment and optimisation framework for symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) in the water sector. These SCES are meant to produce multiple benefits such as increased resource efficiency, and decreased environmental impact, among others. The solutions need to be assessed and compared using a comprehensive set of criteria and indicators. This report discusses key concepts, explains methods, and briefly presents a spreadsheet tool developed for conducting the assessment. The report is divided into four main parts:

- The first part introduces and explains key concepts such as efficiency and circular economy. Several resources may be recovered from water related SCES and thus, commonly recovered resources are classified. The circularity assessment method called material circularity indicator (MCI) is next introduced. This is followed by an expansion of the scope of MCI to fit the resources relevant to the SCES. Equations for the resource categories are developed and presented. The section then moves on to defining efficiency as a ratio between the benefits and costs of an SCES. Two categories of cost indicators are introduced followed by three categories of benefit indicators. By combining different cost and benefit indicators, a total of eleven efficiency indicators are defined, such as simple material efficiency, service unit-based energy efficiency, and service unit ecoefficiency. Circularity and efficiency assessment methods are explained with simple examples, and screenshots from the spreadsheet assessment tool are presented.
- In the second part, a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) method called compromise programming (CP) is explained. There may be several alternative symbiotic solutions that need to be compared on various criteria, such as the ones mentioned in the first part of this report to choose an optimal solution. This decision-making process is aided by the CP tool. The tool allows a user to assign different weights to the criteria indicators to account for varying perspectives. The CP tool is explained with an example and screenshots of the spreadsheet tool are presented.
- The third part discusses mathematical optimisation as another tool for decision-making support with regard to water-related SCES, taking a value-chain perspective. This tool is especially applicable in complex situations when discrete alternatives cannot be defined. The underlying optimisation model with parameters, constraints, objective functions, and decision variables is presented. Finally, the optimisation tool and its relation to the remainder of the WIDER UPTAKE project are explained.
- The fourth part of the report is meant for examples to demonstrate the application of the various methods. Semi-hypothetical case studies are used from the WIDER UPTAKE project to demonstrate the methods of circularity and efficiency assessment, and MCDA.

In conclusion, the assessment and optimisation frameworks developed can be applied to symbiotic circular economy solutions to provide a comprehensive assessment. Circularity assessment of SCES can be achieved at the level of resource categories. The framework allows users to calculate eleven types of efficiency indicators and provides scope for the development of additional indicators based on the needs of a particular case study. The CP-MCDA method helps decision-makers to include different criteria and indicators and to find an optimal decision for SCES development by accounting for various perspectives. Lastly, the optimisation method helps in the decision-making process, in particular in complex situations, when discrete alternative solutions are not available.

Definitions and Terminology

Biological cycle – It is the material resource cycle containing resources that can safely cycle in and out of the biosphere.

Biosphere – Natural regions of the earth's surface and atmosphere occupied by metabolically active living organisms.

Circular economy - Circular economy (CE) is defined here as a concept for a restorative and regenerative economic system (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

Efficiency - It can be broadly defined as the ratio between intended effects (benefits) and the inventoried flows (of resources, energy, money, etc.) or impacts (Huysman et al., 2015).

Industrial symbiosis – Engaging traditionally distinct industries in an exchange of materials, energy, and by-products to gain a competitive advantage (Chertow, 2007).

Linear flow – The part of material flows that are produced from virgin resources and disposed as unrecovered waste or incinerated (as in landfill, energy recovery, etc.)

Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis - It is a method to select the best solution (from a set of pre-specified solutions) by using multiple evaluation criteria/indicators, together with associated decision-makers' preferences (Cinelli et al., 2020).

Optimisation – Mathematical approach to find suggestions for solutions that satisfy a set of constraints in the best possible way.

Recycle – It is the process of recovering material resources to feed them back into a process as crude feedstock (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

Regeneration rate – It is the time rate at which a biotic resource is produced in nature. It relates the growth of the resources with its stock (Klaassen & Opschoor, 1991).

Regenerative flow – Return flows of renewable resources to preserve and enhance their renewability (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

Restorative flow – The part of material flows that originates from reused or recycled sources and ends up getting restored through reuse or recycling (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

Reuse – It is the introduction of a material resource for the same purpose as its original use (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

Technical cycle – It is the material resource cycle containing resources that cannot safely cycle in and out of the biosphere and are meant to cycle within the technosphere.

Technosphere – It refers to the physical environment built or modified by humans. It is a sub-system of the biosphere.

Value chain/network – It is a representation of all steps required to produce goods and services, from input resources / raw materials to the final product; often expressed through the involved entities and their relations

Virgin flows – Material flows that are not from reuse, recycling, or biological materials from sustained production (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

Waste – Any non-productive output of a process that is meant to be discarded (Kurdve et al., 2015).

1 Introduction

The water sector is responsible for delivering important societal services, such as water resource management, water supply, and treatment. These services are essential for maintaining human and environmental health. While great progress has been made to expand access to improved drinking water and sanitation, 2 billion people still lack access to safe drinking water and 3.2 billion people lack safe sanitation services (WHO/UNICEF, 2020). Fulfilling the water needs of a growing population requires significant energy, material, and financial resources. For example, wastewater treatment plants were found to be responsible for nearly 1% of the total electricity consumption of European cities (Maktabifard et al., 2018). Simultaneously, the urban water cycle is a source of valuable resources that remain untapped (Van Der Hoek et al., 2016). These resources can be recovered to offset part of the resource requirement of the water sector or for use in other sectors, such as agriculture and energy generation. This will help in not only managing water resources in a manner that avoids scarcity and pollution but also in ensuring that valuable resources embedded in water streams are recovered, thus building a 'water smart' economy. Hence, not only can the resource use intensity of the water sector be reduced but also other sectors can benefit from these recovered resources.

Symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) are being developed to improve resource efficiency, reduce emissions, and develop sustainable resource recovery businesses in the water sector. These SCES are symbiotic, which means that they link traditionally independent sectors through the exchange of materials and/or energy to improve the efficiency of the whole cluster of sectors. Furthermore, SCES are aiming towards a circular economy, where resources are retained longer in value chains to improve resource efficiency and reduce waste. While developing SCES, several important decisions must be taken related to the choice of resources to recover, the recovery technology, and the application of the recovered resources. Also, numerous decision criteria need to be accounted for such as circularity, energy efficiency, and financial efficiency. Thus, to assess and compare the circularity and efficiency improvement achieved by different SCES, a framework is required. The framework presented in this report is a collection of methods and tools to assess the efficiency and circularity of SCES and to support decision-making using multi-criteria decision analysis and (formal) mixed-integer optimisation.

This report is a deliverable under the WIDER UPTAKE project (EU Horizon 2020 grant no. 869283). It contains explanations of key concepts, such as circularity, efficiency, MCDA, and optimisation. Furthermore, it explains methods for circularity and efficiency assessment of SCES, using semi-hypothetical case studies. There are five case studies as part of the project, located in the Czech Republic, Ghana, Italy, Netherlands, and Norway. The scope of these case studies ranges from product to actor/value chain level, calling for different levels of detail on technical, environmental, and economic aspects. Hence, different approaches are called for to assess and optimise the cases. Multi-criteria decision analysis can help in decision-making when alternatives are well defined with a high level of technical details. Formal optimisation approaches, on the other hand, can find suggestions for new, also non-intuitive solutions, in particular with respect to continuous choices, under often abstracted conditions. Thus, the economic and environmental potential inherent in given situations and ways to attain this potential can be explored.

The Norwegian and Ghanaian cases have a broad perspective, focusing on value chains, possibilities for industrial symbioses, and resource flows rather than on specific processes and material/product compositions such as the Dutch, Czech and Italian cases. In the latter cases, discrete alternatives are defined and thus, MCDA is better suited. The former,

however, often includes decisions of a continuous nature such as capacities or amounts of resources to produce in addition to many discrete (also binary) decisions, and formal optimisation is a more suitable approach. This report describes both approaches and outlines how they can be applied to the case studies in WIDER UPTAKE. A subsequent report, deliverable D3.2 of the project, will show how the framework described here is adapted to case-specific tools that help to identify optimal symbiotic solutions for all case studies.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a classification of relevant resources that may be recovered from water. Methods to assess the circularity and efficiency of water related SCES are also introduced in Section 2. The scope of the material circularity indicator method is expanded to include resources relevant to water sector SCES. Various indicators for costs and benefits are introduced to define different kinds of efficiencies. An MCDA method called compromise programming, meant to optimise symbiotic solutions is described in section 3. Section 4 discusses how formal optimisation approaches can be utilized in the context of WIDER UPTAKE. The methods are then demonstrated by way of semi-hypothetical case studies in section 5. Section 6 presents the summary of the report and main conclusions.

2 Methodology for Circularity and Efficiency Assessment

2.1 General

This section presents the methodology for the circularity and efficiency assessment of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES). The circularity and efficiency assessment are based on annual inflows and outflows of material resources, energy, financial investments, and revenue. This assessment is done in two phases: the resource recovery (RR) phase and the resource application (RA) phase. Details of the method are explained in the following sections.

2.2 Circularity Assessment

2.2.1 Introduction

Circular economy (CE) is defined here as a concept for a restorative and regenerative economic system (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019). Within the CE concept, there is a differentiation between technical and biological cycles. The technical cycle consists of resources that cannot freely enter the biosphere and thus, must be circulated within the economy to extract maximum value (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019; Navare et al., 2021). In contrast, the biological cycle contains resources that can safely cycle in and out of the biosphere since these resources flow in natural biogeochemical cycles (Navare et al., 2021). Resource flows that originate from reused or recycled sources and/or get reused or recycled at the end of their use phase are called restorative (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019). Regenerative refers to the returning of biotic resources to the natural environment such that the resources remain biologically accessible and the production capacity of the natural source is maintained (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019). The circular economy aims to reduce virgin resources and unrecovered waste through restoration and regeneration. To measure progress towards the CE achieved through SCES, circularity needs to be defined. Based on the aforementioned CE definition, circularity of symbiotic circular economy solutions (SCES) is defined here as the extent to which material resource flows have been made restorative and regenerative by these solutions.

The circularity assessment method proposed here is based on the Material Circularity Indicator (MCI) approach developed by Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2019). At the core of the original MCI method is the difference between the linear and restorative flows. Restorative flows are defined as the ones that are restored through reuse and recycling, whereas linear flows originate from virgin resources and terminate their life in landfills or energy recovery facilities (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2019).

SCES often involve a combination of technical and biological cycles. The original MCI method was developed for the technical cycle resources and later extended to include biological resources. Yet, direct application of the original MCI method to water-related resource recovery solutions is not possible because of the restricted way in which linear and restorative flows have been defined. To illustrate this point, we take the example of nitrogen recovery from wastewater and its application to agriculture. Application of nitrogen to agriculture can lead to flows such as nitrate leaching which effectively translates to the loss of the nutrient. Therefore, even though nitrogen does not end up in landfills or energy recovery processes, the leaching of nitrate is a form of linear flow since the resource is lost for all practical purposes. A similar argument can be used for water and water-related resources such as phosphorus. Therefore, definitions of linear and restorative flows need to

be extended for the water-related symbiotic solutions and a more generalised classification of recovered resources needs to be accomplished. Such a classification is presented in the net section.

2.2.2 Generalised classification of recovered resources

The way resource efficiency is calculated and interpreted depends on the type of resource considered (Huysman et al., 2015). There is a wide variety of resources that may be recovered from water. Defining restorative/regenerative and linear flows for each of them is impractical. Therefore, we classify the most common resources into four categories (see

Table 1). This table also provides the relevant extended definitions of linear and restorative flows for water-related resources.

Table 1: Linear and restorative flows for defining circularity of different categories of materials

Material category	Linear flow	Restorative/regenerative flow
Abiotic or mixed resources	Originates from virgin extraction and ends in a landfill or energy recovery process.	Originates from a reused or recycled source and ends up getting reused or recycled.
Biotic (renewable resources)	Appropriation rate higher than the regeneration rate and ends up in a landfill or energy recovery process.	Appropriation rate lower than the regeneration rate and ends up getting reused, recycled, or composted.
Nutrients	Nitrogen that originates from industrial conversion of unreactive N ₂ that ends up dissipated as reactive emission (e.g., N ₂ O) to air or water bodies.	Nitrogen that originates from reused or recycled sources that ends up as biomass accumulation or unreactive emission.
	Phosphorus that originates from phosphate rocks that ends up dissipated in water bodies.	Phosphorus that originates from reused or recycled sources that ends up as biomass accumulation or fixed in the soil.
Water	Originates from a natural water source and ends up evaporated or discharged with a significantly lower quality than a receiving body.	Originates from a reuse or recycle source and ends up getting recycled, reused, or discharged with appropriate quality.

Abiotic or mixed materials

This category includes resources that originate from non-living matter such as metals, minerals, synthetic materials, or originate from fossilized organic matter such as fossil fuels. This category is characterized by a finite stock and non-renewability. For resources belonging to this category, restorative and linear flows are defined as in the original MCI methodology. Therefore, flows that originate from virgin extraction that end up in landfills or energy recovery processes constitute linear flows. Flows that originate from reuse or recycled sources that end up being reused or recycled after use comprise restorative flows.

Biotic materials

These resources originate from living organisms and examples include aquatic plants and biological sludge. The appropriation rate of such resources refers to the quantity of the resource collected for human use in a year. Regeneration rate is the time rate of production of the biotic resource. The regeneration rate relates the growth of the resources with its stock (Klaassen & Opschoor, 1991). In this report, biotic materials are inherently considered renewable if their appropriation rates are maintained lower than their regeneration rates.

Therefore, linear flows for biotic materials can be defined as flows that have their appropriation rate greater than regeneration rate and that end up in landfills (banned in some countries) or energy recovery processes. For biotic materials, the possibility of composting has to be included while defining restorative flows. Thus, restorative flows are those that have an appropriation rate smaller than the regeneration rate and they are reused, recycled, or composted after use.

Nutrients

This category includes nitrogen (N) and phosphorous (P), which are commonly occurring nutrients in wastewater. Atmospheric nitrogen is fixed in reactive forms through natural and artificial processes. Of the artificial processes, the Haber-Bosch process is the most widely used (Cherkasov et al., 2015). Nitrogen fixed through this process accounts for nearly doubling of the total N fixed in the last century (Schlesinger & Bernhardt, 2020). Nitrogen (N) waste can be attributed mainly to the losses of N caused by ammonia volatilization, ammonia discharge into the aquatic environment, denitrification, runoff, nitrate leaching, and nitrogen oxide emissions (NO_x , N_2O) (Raun & Johnson, 1999; Slootweg, 2020; Zhu & Chen, 2002). While denitrification of nitrogen oxides to N_2 is also a form of industrial emission, it is largely free from adverse implications (Mosier et al., 2004). Therefore, unreactive nitrogen (N_2) emissions are here considered a form of restorative flow. To define restorative and linear flows of nutrients, we make use of their biogeochemical cycles. For nitrogen, we developed a simple reservoir model as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of nitrogen cycle. The red arrows represent linear flows; the blue arrows denote restorative flows.

We define linear flows of nitrogen as those that originate from industrial conversion of unreactive N_2 to reactive nitrogen species, predominantly through the Haber-Bosch process and end up as reactive nitrogen emission to air or water bodies. On the contrary, regenerative flows are those that originate from reuse or recycled sources and end up as biomass accumulation, soil fixation, or unreactive emissions.

For phosphorus, the primary source is phosphate rocks (Boer et al., 2018; Smol, 2019). Phosphorus is largely un-substitutable but can be reused repeatedly (Withers et al., 2015). In the current management of P, large dissipation of the element can be noted into low-grade ores, manure, surface water, groundwater, and the oceans (Withers et al., 2015). Weathering of rocks by flowing water that carries P to the ocean is the largest flux of P in the ecosystem (Schlesinger & Bernhardt, 2020). The P in ocean water eventually gets sedimented on the

ocean floor. Over several millions of years, these sediments are uplifted and again subjected to weathering, thus completing the phosphorus cycle (Schlesinger & Bernhardt, 2020). Since the P cycle takes millions of years to renew the P stocks back into forms that can be mined, P is not renewed in a time scale relevant to humans and should be categorized as a non-renewable resource. We define linear flows for P as those that originate from phosphate rocks and other virgin sources and that end up dissipated in surface water, groundwater, rivers, or oceans. Regenerative flows are those that originate from reuse/recycle sources and end up as biological accumulation. A simple reservoir model of flows and reservoirs of P is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Schematic representation of phosphorus cycle. The red arrows represent linear flows; blue arrows denote restorative flows.

Water

Even though water flows in a renewable hydrological cycle, the spatio-temporal distribution of its supply and demand can lead to water scarcity (Arora et al., 2022). Three possibilities exist for the destination of water after use: (1) it may be returned to a WWTP for further treatment; (2) it may be reused for the same or another application; (3) it may be discharged to the natural environment (river/groundwater or lake/sea). Linear flows for water can be defined as water flows obtained from natural sources such as groundwater and surface water and that end up evaporated or lost in any other way for the water bodies or human use. Regenerative flows are here defined as those that originate from recycled or reused sources and end up either getting reused/recycled, discharged with appropriate quality into the receiving body, or assimilated by a living organism (e.g., water contained in crops).

2.2.3 Circularity Assessment Method

Having defined restorative/regenerative and linear flows for relevant resource categories in the previous section, we can extend the original MCI model for these resources. Here, we explain how the original MCI equations can be adapted for nitrogen as an example. The complete set of equations for the four resource categories of Table 1 is shown in Appendix 0.

In the case of Nitrogen, virgin flows are the ones that originate from the industrial fixation of atmospheric N₂. Conversely, nitrogen flow can be considered regenerative when the flow is reused for a particular application (through internal recycling) or obtained from a recycled

source (e.g., from a wastewater treatment plant). Hence, the equation for estimating virgin nitrogen extraction can be written as follows:

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U) \quad (1)$$

where V is the annual virgin mass flow of Nitrogen (kg/y), M is the annual mass flow of nitrogen through a process (kg/y), F_R is the fraction of the nutrient recycled from sources such as wastewater and F_U is the fraction of the nutrient internally reused.

Similarly, linear flow after use, (i.e., unrecovered waste) can be defined as all reactive nitrogen flows that are dissipated into air or water through losses such as leaching, volatilization, runoff, and emission. We consider any N incorporated into biomass, fixed in the soil, or returned to the atmosphere as N_2 to be restorative flows. Hence, to estimate unrecovered waste we use the following equation:

$$W = M(1 - C_{imm} - C_S - C_P - C_{UR}) \quad (2)$$

where W is the annual unrecovered nitrogen waste flow (kg/y), M is the annual mass flow of N used in an application (kg/y), C_{imm} represents the fraction of N assimilated by microorganisms, C_S represents the fraction of N fixed into the soil, C_P is the fraction of N taken up by plants, and C_{UR} is the fraction of N returned to the atmosphere as unreactive N_2 .

Now, the linear flow of nitrogen through a process can be calculated using the following equation:

$$LFI = \frac{V+W}{2M} \quad (3)$$

where LFI is the linear flow indicator of nitrogen flows, V is the annual virgin mass flow rate of Nitrogen (kg/y), W is the annual unrecovered nitrogen waste (kg/y), and M is the annual mass flow of N used in an application (kg/y).

Finally, the material circularity indicator for nitrogen can be calculated using the following equation:

$$MCI_{nitrogen} = 1 - LFI \quad (4)$$

where $MCI_{nitrogen}$ is the material circularity indicator for nitrogen, and LFI is the linear flow indicator for nitrogen.

The material circularity indicators enable us to calculate how restorative and regenerative a given process is. In other words, these indicators can tell us what fraction of mass flows (both input and output) of a process can be considered as contributing towards a circular economy transition. A value of 0 means the process is completely linear, whereas a value of 1 represents a completely circular process.

MCI Calculation Example

To calculate the MCI, it is necessary to have the following: the list of material resources flowing in and out of the analysed RR or RA phase, flow rates (mass or volume) of these resources, their origins, and their destinations. Below, we explain the steps involved in calculating the MCI. These steps must be repeated for each resource category separately.

To explain the steps, we show an example of using WWTP effluent for garden irrigation (see Figure 3). In this example, a total of 100 m³/y of water is required for irrigation of which 60 m³/y is obtained from a WWTP effluent while the rest is diverted from a nearby river. Upon application to the garden, we assume 10 m³/y of water is lost to evapotranspiration, whereas

40 m³/y seeps into the ground and replenishes groundwater storage. 30 m³/y of the garden run-off is collected and stored for further reuse. 10 m³/y of water is lost as runoff and another 10 m³/y is assumed to form crop water content.

Figure 3 - Mass flow model of an irrigation process that uses effluent from a WWTP. Red arrows represent linear flows; blue arrows denote restorative flows.

The calculation of MCI in the above example involves the following steps:

1. Estimate the total mass or volume of a resource flowing into a process.
Total volume of water flowing into the irrigation process $M = 100 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
2. Estimate the fraction of mass or volume of the resource that originates from reuse/recycled sources.
Total volume of water flowing from reuse source = $60 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
Fraction of water flowing from reuse source (F_{WWTP}) = 0.6
3. Calculate the mass or volume of virgin resource by subtracting the fraction of reuse/recycled resources from total resource input.
Virgin water extraction $V = M(1 - F_{\text{WWTP}} - F_U - F_R)$
 $V = 100(1 - 0.6 - 0 - 0)$
 $V = 40 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
4. Estimate the fraction of the resource that gets reused/recycled/discharged/assimilated after use in the process.
Volume of water discharged after use (assuming sufficient quality) = $40 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
Fraction of water discharged = 0.4
Volume of water collected for recycling = $30 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
Fraction of water collected for recycling = 0.3
Volume of water assimilated into crops = $10 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
Fraction of water assimilated into crops = 0.10
5. Calculate the total mass or volume of unrecoverable waste by subtracting the fraction of resource reused/recycled after use from the total resource inflow.
Total unrecoverable water volume $W = M(1 - C_{\text{WWTP}} - C_U - C_R - C_D - C_{\text{BA}})$
 $W = 100(1 - 0 - 0 - 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.1)$
 $W = 20 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
6. Calculate the total linear flows as the sum of virgin extraction and unrecovered waste mass.
Total linear flow of water ($V+W$) = $40 + 20 = 60 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$
7. Calculate the linear flow indicator as ratio between total linear flow and two times the total resource mass.
Linear Flow Indicator of water $\text{LFI} = 60/200 = 0.3$

8. Calculate the material circularity indicator by subtracting LFI from 1.
Material circularity indicator of water $MCI = 1 - 0.3 = 0.7$

The obtained MCI value of 0.7 means that 70% of the water flows can be considered circular in this example.

2.2.4 Circularity Assessment Tool

The circularity assessment spreadsheet tool has two input sheets and an output sheet. The two input sheets are for resource recovery and resource application phases. In the input sheet, a user finds the resource categories (discussed in Section 2.2.2) mentioned.

	A	B	C
1	Circularity assessment		
2	Alternative 1		
3	Resource category	Unit	Value
4	Abiotic or mixed resources		
26	Biotic resources		
36	Water		
37	Total water	m ³ /y	100
38	Fraction of water obtained from WWTP (F _{WWTP})	Fraction	0.6
39	Fraction of water reused within the same process (F _U)	Fraction	0
40	Fraction of water originating from another application process (F _R)	Fraction	0
41	Fraction of water going to a WWTP after use (C _{WWTP})	Fraction	0
42	Fraction of water reused within the same application process (C _U)	Fraction	0
43	Fraction of water going into another use process (C _R)	Fraction	0.3
44	Fraction of water discharged with a quality suitable to the receiving body (C _D)	Fraction	0.4
45	Total virgin mass	kg	40
46	Total unrecovered waste mass	kg	30
47	Nutrients		

Figure 4 - Screenshot of the circularity assessment input sheet of the assessment tool

Under those categories, the user may enter the name of a resource, its total mass or volume flowing in a particular phase, its fractions from reuse/recycled sources, and fractions of the resource going into processes such as reuse, recycle, composting, etc. Upon entering all this data, the sheet shows the results related to total virgin quantity, total unrecovered waste quantity, the linear flow index, and the material circularity indicator of the resource. A screenshot of the input sheet is shown in Figure 4.

Once all relevant resources have been entered and their MCIs calculated, the user may check the complied results in the output sheet shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Screenshot of the circularity assessment output sheet that shows the results of circularity for all relevant resource categories in tabulated and graphical forms for each of the compared alternatives. AMCI stands for abiotic material circularity indicator, BMCI for biotic material circularity indicator, WCI for water circularity indicator, and NCI for nutrient circularity indicator.

2.3 Efficiency Assessment Method

2.3.1 Introduction

Efficiency refers to the capacity of a process to produce a desired result with minimum energy, time, material, or money expenditure (Merriam-Webster, 2022). Thus, efficiency can be broadly defined as the ratio between intended effects (benefits) and the inventoried flows (of resources, energy, money, etc.) or impacts. Along similar lines, Huysman et al., (2015) defined two levels of efficiency: level 1 refers to the ratio between benefits and inventoried flows and level 2 is the ratio between the intended effects or benefits and the environmental impact (more commonly known as ecoefficiency). In this report, we present a set of efficiency indicators based on different benefit and cost indicators that a user of our tool may select. This framework for efficiency assessment developed is shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 6 - Framework for efficiency assessment of SCES in the water sector. In this framework, the cost can be expressed with total resource input (RI) or the life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) of an SCES. Benefits may be expressed in service units (SU), auxiliary service units (ASU), or resource output (RO). Simple efficiencies are dimensionless ratios of RO to RI. SU-based efficiencies can be calculated using total RI to give SU-RI efficiency or LCIA to calculate SU-ecoefficiency and the same goes for ASU-RI and ASU-ecoefficiency.

2.3.2 Benefits

There are several ways to quantify benefits related to symbiotic solutions. Through recovery and reuse of resources, there may be financial, material, energy, or health and environmental benefits. Moreover, the benefits may be enjoyed by a water treatment plant, users served by the treatment plant, users of the recovered resource, the natural environment or society in general. Some options for quantifying benefits and calculating efficiency improvements are presented below.

The most straightforward way to quantify benefits is to use service units of a process. Service unit refers to the actual product/service provided by a process for society (Mancini et al., 2012). The service unit-material resource efficiency is defined as follows:

$$Eff_{SU-mat} = \frac{SU}{MIR} \quad (5)$$

where Eff_{SU-mat} is the service unit-material resource efficiency, SU is a service unit of a process. The SU can be expressed in terms of the primary function that a process provides. MIR is the material resources input rate (kg/y).

To illustrate, suppose a water softening process, treating $2 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$ of water, uses 1000 kg/y of mineral resources as input. The resource efficiency of the process would be $2000 \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$ ($= 2\,000\,000 \text{ m}^3 / 1000 \text{ kg}$). Now, if through resource recovery, half of the mineral input can be reused, then the process continues to treat $2 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ of water with 500 kg of mineral resources. This would improve the service unit material efficiency to $4000 \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}$. Therefore, service unit efficiency improvement implies that the process can provide the same quantity of service with lower resource inputs.

Some processes may have several auxiliary functions in addition to a primary function. For example, the primary function of a wastewater treatment plant may be to treat $2 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ of domestic wastewater, while recovering phosphorus to supply a fertilizer manufacturer may be an auxiliary service. One can calculate the auxiliary service efficiency of a resource recovery or application process. To illustrate, suppose 2000 kg phosphorus can be supplied for fertilizer production and the recovery process requires an additional 50 kWh/y, then the energy efficiency of providing the auxiliary service of phosphorus supply can be calculated as follows:

$$Eff_{ASU-en} = \frac{Q_p}{EIR} \quad (6)$$

where Eff_{ASU-en} is the auxiliary service-based energy efficiency of the recovery process, Q_p is the quantity of phosphorus supplied for fertilizer production, EIR is the energy input rate to the process (kWh/y). Therefore, the environmental efficiency Eff_{ASU-en} in the above example is $2000/50 = 40 \text{ kg/kWh}$.

Another way to measure benefit, especially suited for resource recovery processes, is by simply quantifying the useful outputs of a process. Useful outputs can be material resources, energy, or income that are obtained as a result of a resource recovery process. These indicators can be used with material and energy resource input indicators to calculate simple efficiencies. These simple efficiencies are dimensionless since they are calculated as ratios between input and outputs of the same type of resource (energy/material/financial).

$$Eff_{mat} = \frac{MOR}{MIR} \quad (7)$$

where Eff_{mat} is a simple material resource efficiency, MOR is the annual material resource output rate (kg/y), and MIR is the annual material resource input rate (kg/y).

To illustrate, suppose a water softening process takes 1000 kg/y of material resource input, and 500 kg/y resources are recovered from the softener for further use, then the resource efficiency (Eff_{mat}) of the process would be 0.5 (=500/1000).

A longer list of potential benefit indicators can be found in Appendix 8.2.

2.3.3 Cost indicators

Similar to benefits, costs can be expressed in different terms such as material resources used, waste produced, energy used, financial investment and environmental impacts. Also, the costs may be from the perspective of a treatment plant, human society, or some other stakeholder. Therefore, we present a collection of cost indicators to cover these options.

The first option is to directly use quantities of material resources and waste in kg/y or m³/y, energy resources in kWh/y, and/or financial investment in €/y. The second option is to express costs in environmental impact units which can be calculated using Life Cycle Assessment. Based on these options, two categories of efficiency indicators may be calculated.

Level 1 efficiency

To calculate level 1 efficiency, the denominator can be an indicator that measures the annual material resource input rate, waste production rate, energy use rate, or financial investment rate. To illustrate, suppose a filtration process unit has to be added to an existing WWTP to purify water for reuse. We assume the annual cost of the WWTP was 620 000 €/y. The annualized investment cost of the added filtration unit is 20 000 €/y. The treatment plant has an annual influent volume of 2 000 000 m³/y. The user wants to apply a SU-based benefit indicator along with total financial investment as the cost indicator to compare how the financial efficiency of delivering a service unit changes due to the added unit process. In this case, efficiency may be calculated using the following equation:

$$Eff_{SU-fi} = \frac{SU}{FIR} \quad (8)$$

where Eff_{SU-fi} is the service unit-based financial efficiency of a process, SU is the service unit of a process, FIR is the financial input rate required to set up and run the process (€/y).

Thus, for the base line WWTP efficiency can be calculated as follows:

$$Eff_{SU-fi} = \frac{2\,000\,000}{620\,000} = 3.23 \text{ m}^3/\text{€} \quad (9)$$

And for the WWTP supplemented with a filtration process, efficiency would be as follows:

$$Eff_{SU-fi} = \frac{2\,000\,000}{640\,000} = 3.13 \text{ m}^3/\text{€} \quad (10)$$

Thus, for level 1 efficiency assessment, the user only needs to enter mass flows of material resources or wastes, energy used, or financial investment. The disadvantage lies in the lack of discrimination between different types of resource and waste flows, whereas ease of calculation is an advantage.

Level 2 efficiency

While level 1 efficiency is based on costs at the level of flows of resources, level 2 efficiency estimates the costs in terms of environmental impacts associated with these flows. Since

environmental relevance can vary dramatically for different kinds of resources and wastes (Hauschild & Huijbregts, 2015), one needs to use characterized impacts of the resource and waste flows. These characterized impacts may be calculated using Life Cycle Assessment.

Life Cycle Assessment

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a method to calculate environmental impacts over the life cycle of a product using characterization models (Rebitzer et al., 2004). These models help to calculate characterization factors for resource and waste flows, translating the flow quantities (expressed in units such as kg, kWh or m³) into impacts on a particular environmental category (Hauschild & Huijbregts, 2015). There are several characterization models available such as CML 2002, Eco-indicator 99, EDIP 2003, and ReCiPe 2016, among others, however, no single method enjoys universal acceptance (Hauschild et al., 2013).

Due to the lack of universal acceptance of a single characterization method, we make a choice to use ReCiPe 2016 for our framework. Our choice is because the ReCiPe model has one of the widest ranges of mid-point indicators (18 in total) and the model also allows for end-point characterization (3 categories). **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the ReCiPe mid-point categories, end-point categories, and the damage pathways in between them.

Figure 7 - Overview of the ReCiPe 2016 mid-point and end-point categories (Huijbregts et al., 2016).

The ReCiPe method translates LCI results, which are a list of used resources, produced waste and emissions, into mid-point environmental impact categories. This is achieved through a set of characterization factors unique to the ReCiPe method. The conversion of resource/waste flows into mid-point impacts is done as follows:

$$I_m = \sum_i Q_{mi} \cdot m_i \quad (11)$$

where m_i is the mass or volume magnitude of a resource or waste flow, Q_{mi} is the characterization factor for the particular flow, and I_m is the indicator result for a mid-point impact category m .

Similarly, the translation of mid-point impacts into end-point categories is achieved by the following equation:

$$I_e = \sum_m Q_{em} \cdot I_m \quad (12)$$

where I_m is a mid-point indicator, Q_{em} is the characterization factor that connects a mid-point category m to an end-point category e , and I_e is the indicator result for an end-point impact category e .

Error! Reference source not found. shows how elementary flows are converted to mid-point impacts and eventually to end-point categories in the ReCiPe method.

Figure 8 - Example to illustrate mid-point and end-point characterization used in ReCiPe method (Goedkoop & Huijbregts, 2013).

We provide two options for calculating the environmental impacts: the full life cycle approach and the direct impact approach. In the full life cycle approach, the user conducts an LCA of the RR and RA processes separately using the ReCiPe 2016 method. We also offer a simplified alternative to using an LCA wherein, users have an option to directly calculate the environmental impacts of a process when a complete LCA is not possible, due to lack of time or resources. In this approach, we make two forms of simplifications:

1. We only account for direct emissions from the resource recovery and application processes instead of considering the entire life cycle.
2. We use a non-exhaustive list of relevant emissions and their characterization factors.

Based on a literature review done by (Zang et al., 2015), the environmental impact categories most relevant to water treatment plants are global warming potential, eutrophication potential, toxicity, acidification, photochemical oxidant potential, ozone layer depletion, energy use, land and water use. We briefly describe these impact categories and provide characterization factors for common compounds in Appendix 8.5. However, this list is not comprehensive and final. Since the choice of environmental impact categories depends

upon the nature of a particular case study and its surrounding environment, the relevant categories will be individually determined while assessing these case studies.

In the end, i.e., upon using either the complete LCA or the simplified option, a list of environmental impacts associated with an RR or RA process can be generalised. These impact indicators can be combined with benefit indicators, discussed in section 2.3.2, to provide estimate or level 2 efficiency, also known as ecoefficiency. The equation to calculate ecoefficiency takes the following form:

$$Eff_{eco} = \frac{BI}{LCIA_i} \quad (13)$$

where Eff_{eco} is the ecoefficiency of a process, BI is the benefit indicator estimating a benefit resulting from the process, and $LCIA_i$ is the life cycle impact assessment result for an environmental impact category i . Users also have an option to use aggregated environmental impact scores (e.g., end-point ReCiPe categories and shadow pricing).

To illustrate, suppose a user wants to calculate ecoefficiency of a case wherein an ultraviolet (UV) disinfection unit is used to produce irrigation water from 2×10^5 m³/y WWTP effluent. We assume the UV disinfection requires 0.13 kWh/m³ energy based on Fenu et al. (2010) and the energy is sourced from a coal-based power plant. A total energy generation of 26 000 kWh/y leads to certain environmental impacts. A quick LCA on Simapro tells us that the total freshwater eco-toxicity impact of this energy generation is 685 kg 1,4-DCB. Also, we assume, the user expresses the benefit in the form of useful output (i.e., 2×10^5 m³/y of irrigation water). Then, the ecoefficiency of this RR process can be calculated as follows:

$$Eff_{eco} = \frac{200\,000}{685} = 291.97 \text{ m}^3/\text{kg 1,4-DCB} \quad (14)$$

This implies that the UV disinfection process can produce 291.97 m³ of irrigation water with an environmental impact of 1 kg 1,4-DCB of freshwater eco-toxicity.

2.3.4 Efficiency assessment tool

Below, we present screenshots of the efficiency assessment spreadsheet tool. Figure 9 shows the input sheet wherein a user enters the total input and output material, energy, and financial resources. The user has an option to modify the units as long as the units represent the quantity (mass or volume) of flow per year.

	A	B	C
1	Efficiency assessment		
2	Alternative 1		
3	Resource recovery process		
4	Service unit (SU)	t/y	60000000
5	Auxiliary service unit (ASU)		-
6	Item	Unit	Value
7	Total material resource input (TMR)	t/y	7034
8	Total waste (TW)	t/y	4717
9	Total material resource output (reuse/recycle) (TMO)	t/y	535
10	Total energy input (TE)	kWh/y	710000
11	Total energy output (TEO)	kWh/y	0
12	Total financial input (TFI)	€/y	3000
13	Total revenue (TR)	€/y	1500
14			

Figure 9 - Screenshot of the input sheet for efficiency assessment from the spreadsheet tool.

Figure 10 is a screenshot of the output sheet of the efficiency assessment. The table shows the values of simple efficiency of a resource recovery process and the diagram under the table shows the comparison of efficiencies of the three alternatives used as examples.

Figure 10 - Screenshot of the output sheet for efficiency assessment from the spreadsheet tool. The table shows results of a simple efficiency assessment of a resource recovery process while the spider-web chart shows a comparison of three alternative recovery processes.

3 Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis

3.1 Introduction

Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) is a method to select the best alternative solution (from a set of pre-specified options) by using multiple evaluation criteria/indicators, together with associated decision-makers' preferences (Cinelli et al., 2020). MCDA is useful

in decision-making because it explicitly accounts for multiple criteria, structures a decision-making problem and leads to rational and justifiable decisions (Mendoza & Martins, 2006).

The analysed alternative solutions and what is sought from them (e.g., low-cost performance, multiple benefits, low environmental impact, etc.) are typically generated by the domain experts, i.e., people who understand the analysed system (e.g., water treatment experts for wastewater reuse). Once alternatives are defined, decision-makers agree on the list of criteria to be used in the assessment process together with respective preferences (e.g., criteria weights). For symbiotic solution assessment, these criteria could include circularity, efficiency, environmental impact, and other criteria.

Once the above is defined, experts assess the performance of each alternative against the pre-defined list of criteria. This can be done in a number of different ways ranging from using various simulation tools to expert judgement. This results in the creation of the so-called decision matrix of values. This matrix contains the information in terms of how well each of the analysed alternative solutions is performing with respect to the multiple criteria used for the assessment. The MCDA method then ranks the alternative solutions based on this information and different MCDA methods do this in different ways (Hajkovicz & Collins, 2007). Thus, MCDA helps to make objective and systematic decisions.

3.2 Compromise programming method

One MCDA method is the compromise programming (CP) method developed by Zeleny (1974). This method was selected for use here as it is well-known and widely used for making complex decisions in the presence of multiple criteria and different decision-makers' preferences.

The CP method works by identifying an imaginary ideal solution as a point where all criteria achieve their optimal values (Parra et al., 2005). In Figure 11, the ideal solution is represented by the point (F_1^*, F_2^*) . Then, the distance (in the multiple criteria space) is calculated between the ideal point and the actual point corresponding to the analysed alternative solution. The distances estimated this way are used to rank the alternative solutions, from shortest to longest distance to the ideal point. The alternative that is at the least distance from the ideal solution is regarded as the best alternative.

The distance between an alternative and the ideal solution is measured by the following equation:

$$D_{p,j} = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \left(w_i \left| \frac{F_i^* - f_{i,j}}{F_i^* - F_{i*}} \right| \right)^p \right]^{1/p} \quad (15)$$

where w_i is the weight coefficient for criterion i ; the sum of all weights must equal 1, $f_{i,j}$ is the value of criterion i for the j^{th} alternative, F_i^* and F_{i*} are the ideal (largest and smallest) values of $f_{i,j}$ across all alternatives, i.e., ideal values for criterion i , F_i is the anti-ideal solution vector, i.e., the worst value for the i^{th} criterion, p is the distance norm, usually taken as 2, to measure Euclidian type distance, and N_c is the number of assessment criteria.

Figure 11 - The ideal point within the solution space of a two-criteria decision problem. F_1 and F_2 are the two criteria being maximised in this case.

To illustrate this method, we describe an example. Suppose a user has to compare three alternative wastewater treatment plants on the basis of circularity, material resource efficiency, and service unit-energy efficiency. Without going into details of the calculation of indicators involved, we assume indicator values for the three alternatives as shown in Table 2. All three criteria have to be maximized and we assume equal weights (0.33) for each of them. For circularity and material resource efficiency, the ideal and anti-ideal values are 1 and 0. For service unit-energy efficiency, no universally ideal or anti-ideal value exists. Therefore, the highest value among the alternatives can be assumed as the ideal value while the lowest value can be taken as the anti-ideal.

Table 2: Circularity, material resource efficiency, and service unit-energy efficiency of three alternative wastewater treatment plants.

Alternatives	Criteria	Circularity	Material resource efficiency	Service unit-energy efficiency (m ³ /kWh)
	To be	Maximised	Maximised	Maximised
Alternative 1		0.4	0.6	2
Alternative 2		0.8	0.4	1.6
Alternative 3		0.5	0.3	2.5

The distance for each alternative from the ideal point can be calculated using Equation 15 for $p=2$. Assuming equal weights (0.33) for the three criteria, the corresponding distances are 0.303 for alternative 1, 0.394 for alternative 2, and 0.287 for alternative 3. Therefore, alternative 3 lies at the shortest distance from the ideal solution and is ranked first, i.e., as the best alternative.

3.3 CP-MCDA Tool

Figure 12 shows a screenshot of the compromise programming MCDA tool. A user enters the relevant criteria along with their units, weights, normalization minimum, and maximum values and specifies whether the criteria is to be maximised or minimised. Thereafter, the user enters the corresponding values for each of the compared alternatives and the results

are shown on the right side of the spreadsheet. The results include CP distance, i.e., the distance between each alternative and the ideal solution, and the ranks of the alternatives.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Compromise Programming MCDA						
2	Input data				Results		
3	Resource recovery process						
4	Criteria	SU-financial efficiency	SU-material efficiency	SU-energy efficiency	Circularity	CP Distance	Rank
5	Units	m ³ /€	m ³ /kg	m ³ /kWh			
6	User weights	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25		
7	Minimisation?	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE		
8	Normalisation minimum	1800.00	5106.00	65.00	0.00		
9	Normalisation maximum	2050.00	9000.00	90.00	1.00		
10							
11	Default	2000.00	5106.00	84.51	0.20	0.329	3
12	Alternative 1	2050.00	8530.00	90.00	0.40	0.153	1
13	Alternative 2	1900.00	8530.00	90.00	0.76	0.164	2
14	Alternative 3	1800.00	9000.00	65.00	0.80	0.357	4

Figure 12 - Screenshot of the inputs and results sheet of the CP-MCDA tool. A user defines a number of criteria with units, weights, normalization max and min values along with whether the criteria have to be maximised or minimised. The results are shown in terms of distances and ranks of the alternatives.

4 Optimisation of Water-Smart Solutions

4.1 Introduction

Optimisation is widely applied to find good suggestions for design and operation of value chains, showing the ensuing potential for, e.g., profitability and emissions reduction along the whole chain or for single actors. It allows to take into account complex relationships, albeit often simplified. Powerful solution algorithms find, in a systematic manner, also non-intuitive solutions quickly. The methodology helps to explore the (economic, environmental, social) potential of good solutions and interventions in a situation, but also to explore under which circumstances this potential may be reached or what is required such that solutions and interventions can be economically feasible and environmentally friendly.

Typically, new or changed technology and processes will incur costs but may also contribute to generating additional revenue or reducing operational costs. Optimisation and similar analyses show how this can balance out. This offers a base to make good decisions, demonstrating how new solutions may fit within established systems but also how new systems should be formed to be more water smart and environmentally friendly.

Providing also non-intuitive, hitherto not thought-of suggestions, optimisation can help to escape lock-in situations where the network has locked into established technologies and practices. In such situations, progress through innovation is hampered and resources are not used in the most environmentally friendly and efficient ways. Still, such suggestions should be investigated further with respect to their readiness to transition to the chosen suggestion from the current state, at what costs (not only monetary), which incentives would entice actors to transition to new approaches etc.

For industrial symbioses¹, optimisation can find solutions for efficient resource usage (including resources that are currently considered waste) within the symbiosis but also identify "missing" actors or resource conversion processes to make the symbiosis more efficient and more circular. Typically, this is done with economics in mind, but environmental or social aspects may be just as significant.

The basis for an optimisation approach is a mathematical model, i.e., an abstraction of a well-defined real-life situation that is often intentionally held rather simple and focuses on the most important aspects. Such a model consists of constraints describing essential relations and restrictions, an objective function (optimisation goal), decision variables that define suggestions for solutions in the given situation, and parameters to specify the considered situation and context. This way, a quick overview and guidelines can be provided to scout out feasible and good suggestions. These suggestions can then be analysed in detail and refined in dedicated technical approaches.

The following section shows how optimisation approaches can be used in the context of WIDER UPTAKE. Section 4.3 describes a suitable optimisation model while section 4.4 is concerned with an implementation of the model as a software tool to provide decision support. Section 0 outlines how the approach fits with other work in WIDER UPTAKE, in particular with the work on business models (WP 4) and on more holistic water smartness studies (WP 5). Deliverable 3.2 of the WIDER UPTAKE project will describe an application of

¹ Following the definition of industrial symbiosis used in work package 4, this comprises at least three enterprises or nodes in the value chain and at least two resources exchanged.

the tool to two actual case studies, wastewater treatment (WWT) with struvite extraction in Norway and WWT with bio-char production in Ghana.

4.2 Optimisation in the context of WIDER UPTAKE

Of the cases studied in the project, the Norwegian and Ghanaian ones have a broader perspective, focusing on value chains, possibilities for industrial symbioses and resource flows. This includes decisions of a continuous nature (such as capacities or amounts of resources to produce) in addition to many discrete (also binary) decisions, and formal optimisation is a suitable approach. It contributes to exploring the environmental and economic potential of efficient resource use and finds suggestions to attain this potential in a good way.

A value chain is a sequence or network of various nodes or entities that are in a (business) relationship with each other, exchanging resources such as materials and money, but also information, between each other. Figure 13 describes a stylized value chain based on the case in Ghana, with four main entities and the main resource streams (un)treated water and biosolids. The industrial symbiosis network considered here does not comprise the whole circular system, i.e., the complete water cycle comprising use, treatment, re-use etc. Rather, the focus is on treatment of the used water, extraction of valuable resources, and processing these resources such that they offer more environmentally friendly and socially favourable alternatives to currently used products.

Figure 13 - Stylized value chain based on Ghana case study.

From an economics point of view, these value chains and industrial symbioses are governed by a variety of business models. Such business models detail out important participants in the network, their relations, resource streams etc. Work package 4 in the project is concerned with governance and business models for industrial symbiosis on a broader base than considered here. The clusters considered there reflect the multiple layers of the studied business models and may include regulators, policy stakeholders, media, local government agencies etc. For the optimisation approach in WP 3, only operating entities of the value chain – producers, markets etc. – are of interest.

4.3 The WIDER UPTAKE optimisation approach

Considering treatment of wastewater and water smartness, the system has a "push" character:² the wastewater entering the system is not affected by decisions made by actors in the system. Instead, the aim is to improve utilization of resources resulting from the treatment processes.

Consequently, the basic idea for the optimisation tool is to find a suitable capacity and process(es) for the wastewater treatment actor such that a good balance is found between the quantity of resources that can be recovered and the costs and complexity added to the process for doing so. Criteria may not only take in the market perspective with focus on sales of the recovered, possibly processed, resources. For example, a motivation for struvite extraction may be high maintenance expenses and efforts due to scaling in anaerobic digesters – and thus efficiency of the sludge treatment process. In Ghana, drivers are also the scarcity of wooden fuel and contamination risks when using untreated water in urban farming. Policy or regulatory issues may also motivate to optimise the value chain.

This is placed on an actor/value-chain level and takes, hence, a "black box" approach – we are not interested in technical optimisation of the technologies and processes, i.e., finding the best possible process *configurations*. Therefore, resource extraction and treatment are expressed simplified as "recipes" in the form of "x1 units of input resource 1 and x2 units of resource 2 will give y1 units of output resource 1 and z1 units of output resource 2". However, the model allows to select between several process options. The approach focuses primarily on resource flows and not so much on the quality or level of contamination of the recovered resources and how this may affect treatment costs and prices. However, this may become an adaptation to case-specific requirements.

In this report, we describe an optimisation approach that is general to the project, i.e., not case specific, although it has been motivated by the value-chain focused Ghanaian and Norwegian case studies. It is based on the stylized value chain presented above and will be outlined in the next section. In the subsequent tasks 3.2 and 4.3, this approach will be adapted to the specifics of the two case studies, to be described in deliverable D 3.2.

Optimisation model

For the optimisation, the value chain is interpreted as a chain or network of nodes comprising existing but also potential entities in the chain with relations (flows of resources etc.) between them. These nodes can be of different types such as sources (points where resources enter the considered system), processing nodes, markets, and discharge points (nodes where resources leave the considered system – markets allow to earn a revenue for the resources provided, discharge points do not but costs may arise). At processing nodes, there are processes that transform resources into other resources. The processes are assumed to operate steadily, and the model time frame is rather coarse such that the time needed to convert a resource into another is not relevant for the model. A suitable time granularity would be, e.g., weeks or months, being able to capture potential seasonal variations in supply of wastewater or demand for recovered resources. Running the model over a time horizon of several years makes it possible to find solutions that are robust against seasonal variations and to balance investment or construction expenses against maintenance and operation costs.

² As opposed to a "pull" system where input resources should be procured such as to optimally satisfy a given demand.

Decision variables:

- Resource flows entering/exiting the system and between the single nodes in the value chain - continuous
- Establishment/closure of processes at the nodes - binary
- Capacities of processes – continuous

Parameters:

- Which processes can be operated at which node
- Which of these processes are already established
- Factors describing transformation of resource flows (processing "recipes")
- Capacity limits: processes, storage etc.
- Supply of wastewater incl. seasonal variations
- End-user demand for various resources – incl. seasonal variations
- Costs: maintenance and operations of processes (OPEX), establishing and closing down processes (CAPEX), purchasing resources, penalty costs for disposing of unused or unusable resources, etc.
- Revenues: sales price of various resources

Objective function(s):

Various functions are conceivable that are built around economic and environmental indicators, for example

- Maximize revenue
- Minimize costs
- Minimize environmental effects³
- Minimize amount of untreated wastewater⁴
- Maximize circularity
- Maximize efficiency (of resource usage)

When selecting an objective function, it is also important to consider for whom the optimisation should be done – e.g., for single actors in the value chain (e.g., ensuring economic and environmental sustainability for a treatment plant) or for the whole chain (i.e., more from a societal and coordinating point of view). It should also be explored how the individual goals in the case studies are reflected in the chosen objective function formulations in a good way. These points will be studied in deliverable D 3.2.

³ This calls for an additional parameter quantifying the effects in a simplified way, e.g., for each resource leaving the system or related to the transformation of resources.

⁴ This requires another goal to avoid investing in maximum capacity, combine with, e.g., revenue maximization.

Constraints:

Constraints describe technical and economic relations as well as limits or restrictions on the decisions. Major aspects concern:

- Supply: the amount of incoming wastewater is given (e.g., through a profile with seasonal variations) and must be dealt with in the system. One may add an option to actively bypass the treatment process at a cost or subject to requirements.
- Sourcing: where to get resources from that are needed in the various processes (other than wastewater), this becomes especially interesting if there are several sources to choose from, e.g., at different costs. Sources may have an upper limit.
- Capacities: upper limits on production and storage with respect to the resources.
- Establishment/closure of processes at nodes: allows to choose best suited processes
- Production: transformation of resources takes place only if a process is established and not closed down
- Transformation of resources in the single processes follows the "recipes"; no further input or output resources are involved
- Mass balances: everything leaving a node should enter somewhere and vice versa
- Market demands and sales to markets/end users: various formulations, e.g., satisfy demands, set an upper limit (market saturation), satisfy demands also with alternative products but at a penalty cost.
- Dynamic aspects: change of stored amounts of the resources from one time unit to the next; this includes resources entering/exiting the entity as well as input to / output from production.

Circularity and efficiency indicators:

Examples for relevant indicators describing circularity and/or resource efficiency in the context of a value-chain based approach are:

- Ratio of useable resources that exit the considered system vs. the amount of untreated wastewater entering the system
- Ratio of useable resources that exit the system vs. all resources (incl. waste) that exit the system

Such indicators are calculated based on values for parameters and decision variables in the model. They may be included directly in the optimisation model, e.g., as constraints or as part of the objective function. However, the second indicator comprises decision variables (resource flows) in the numerator and in the denominator, leading to a nonlinear expression. Hence, it should be calculated in a post-optimisation step rather than being included directly in the optimisation model as a constraint as it typically would complicate the solution process. For the single cases, also variants of these indicators may be defined, focusing on "interesting" resources such as an indicator for biogas production from sludge or for sludge composting (Preisner et al., 2022). The considered resources may be measured in different units, and a common unit needs to be found.

These indicator examples differ from the ones suggested in section 2, mainly due to a different scope and higher complexity of the latter indicators. For example, the MCI-based circularity indicator follows detailed material resource flows through the whole system. In

addition, it requires knowledge about a linear-flow setup – however, this may be added as a pre-calculated parameter to the optimisation tool. For the level-2-efficiency indicator, an LCA would need to be carried out based on the concerned flows (again, a larger scope than the optimisation approach). Including this indicator directly in an optimisation tool requires the integration of a separate, complex model directly in the solution process, which is prohibitively complicated. However, indicators such as level-1 (cost) efficiency or the MCI-based circularity indicator may be included in the optimisation model in a simplified or otherwise adapted form on a case-by-case basis.

4.4 Implementation as a software tool

The above-described optimisation problem is a mixed-integer linear problem (MILP). It is implemented as a software tool, allowing for quick evaluation of various situations and the provided suggestions for optimal solutions. The suggestions may be detailed further in dedicated technical frameworks.

Input

The input data is organized in an MS Excel file with several sheets describing various aspects of the considered value chain:

- "General": model and tool parameters like optimisation horizon (time periods), discount rate, objective, output file name, graphs over which indicators or optimal variables should be drawn
- "Nodes": all nodes (entities) in the value chain with their ID number, name, type (e.g., source, processing, market/sink)
- "Value chain": which nodes are connected to each other
- "Resources": details of all resources in the system such as ID number, name, purchase or sales prices, whether they are a key resource (wastewater, biosolids etc.), whether all supplied volumes must be processed. Negative sales prices indicate here that there is a penalty cost for disposing of the resource. Figure 14 shows an example for a fictive case.
- "Supply and demand": profiles describing supply and demand of resources over time
- "Storage": storage capacities for the single resources at (processing) nodes
- "Processes": all processes transforming resources with their ID number, name, node where they may be installed, whether they are installed at the start of the optimisation horizon, their costs (installation, removal/closing down, fixed operational costs occurring at each time period, variable operational costs)
- "Processes and resources": ratios of the various resources entering and exiting the transformation processes as well as possible capacity limits to transform the products in each time period.

This input file may be adapted to the requirements of the optimisation tool application to the case studies in tasks 3.2 and 4.3.

Resources					
ID	Name	Must use all supply (0/1)	Purchase price	Sales price	Key resource (0/1)
1	Wastewater	1	0	0	
2	Energy	0	1	0	
3	Material resources	0	2	0	
4	Biosolids		2	2,5	
5	Biochar			5	1
6	Water reused			2	1
7	Nutrients recovered			2	
8	Effluent discharged			-1	
9	Nutrients discharged			-1	

Figure 14 - Example of data input for the optimisation tool describing all resources in the system.

Optimisation model implementation

The model is implemented in [Python](#) using the [Pyomo](#) optimisation package, see Figure 15. This code reads the input parameter values from the MS Excel file, builds the optimisation model, and populates it with the according values, solves the model, does post-optimisation calculations (e.g., circularity indicators), creates graphs and writes selected solution values and graphs to the specified MS Excel file for output data.

```

202 m.existP=pyo.Var(P,N,T,domain=pyo.Binary) # does process p exist at node n in time t?
203 m.estP=pyo.Var(P,N,T, domain = pyo.Binary) # establish process p at node n in time t?
204 m.closeP=pyo.Var(P,N,T, domain=pyo.Binary) # close down process p at node n in time t?
205 # variables - expressions for objective function
206 m.objprofit=pyo.Var() # total profit achieved in the VC over the whole horizon
207 m.objcosts=pyo.Var() # total costs arising
208 m.objcirc=pyo.Var() #circ.indicator as objective function
209 m.indcirc1=pyo.Var() # circ.indicator: useable resources out / MW in
210
211 # define constraints and obj. functions
212
213 ## constraints
214 # Supply - for some resources (e.g., MW), all supplied volume must be treated in the system
215 def c_SupAll(m,r,n,t):
216     return Sup[r,n,t]==sum(m.flow[r,n,nn,t] for nn in NVCS[n])
217
218 # Supply - for other resources, there is an upper limit on the supply
219 def c_SupLim(m,r,n,t):
220     return Sup[r,n,t]>=sum(m.flow[r,n,nn,t] for nn in NVCS[n])
221
222 # Storage
223 def c_Storage(m,r,n,t):
224     # starting conditions (period 1) - no resources in storage yet
225     if t == 0:
226         return m.storage[r,n,t]==sum(m.flow[r,nn,n,t] for nn in NVCP[n])-sum(m.inp[r,p,n,t]
227             +sum(m.outp[r,p,n,t] for p in P) - sum(m.flow[r,n,nn,t] for nn in NVCS[n])
228     else:
229     # all following periods:
230     return m.storage[r,n,t]==m.storage[r,n,t-1]+sum(m.flow[r,nn,n,t] for nn in NVCP[n])-s
231         um(m.outp[r,p,n,t] for p in P) - sum(m.flow[r,n,nn,t] for nn in NVCS[n])

```

Figure 15 - Excerpt of Python implementation of the optimisation model.

Output data

Output data of the optimisation tool are organized in an MS Excel file with the name specified in the data input. The file contains general information about the model solution for the considered situation such as optimal value for the analysed optimisation goal, values for key indicators on circularity, efficiency and economy, status⁵ of the optimiser when solving the model. Further sheets contain optimal values for key decision variables throughout the optimisation horizon, e.g., which processes should be operative at which entity, key resource flows, input, output, economics at each entity, circularity, and efficiency indicators. Finally, the file contains graphs of selected values. Which values are relevant to be displayed in the file is case dependent and will be coordinated in tasks 3.2 and 4.3. Figure 16 shows an example of the output for a fictive case. Here, treatment technology was suggested to be upgraded during time period 4, requiring some more input resources but improving extraction of useable resources and, hence, reducing waste.

4.5 Using the tool in WIDER UPTAKE

The optimisation model and the tool will be adapted and applied to the actual case studies in tasks 3.2 and 4.3. of the project. Task 3.2 demonstrates the application of the optimisation approach to two case studies, providing suggestions for efficient resource usage and optimal value chain specifications for water smartness. Work package 4 is concerned with comprehensive studies on business models, also providing guidelines to identify pathways to industrial symbiosis based on water-smart wastewater solutions in various contexts. The methodology studied and developed there has a broad scope and comprises many layers, also, and in particular, qualitative aspects. The business models detail out important participants in the value network, their relations, resource and information flows, policies etc. In this sense, they provide a framework that encapsulates the optimisation model for the operating value chain developed here. Among others, the complete business models lay out which actor collaborates how with which other actors and about which resource(s) but do, for example, not define the exact volumes exchanged. This way, it is possible to see the impacts of different business for a case (e.g., a need to adapt logistics, more/fewer entities in the symbiosis, changed resource flows, effects on the economic and environmental potential and what would be required to reach this potential).

Work package 5 develops a common framework to assess water smartness, following Water Europe's definition: 1) value of and in water, 2) management of water resources to avoid water scarcity and pollution of groundwater, 3) fostering circular economy and resource efficiency through closed water and resource loops, 4) resilience of water systems against impacts of climate change. It employs a holistic approach, considering technical performance, environmental impact, societal aspects, economy, and governance. Interaction with work packages 2, 3 and 4 provides domain-specific input. The optimisation model discussed in this section addresses, in particular, points 2) and 3), suggesting solutions for best possible circularity and efficiency in wastewater treatment, thus helping to avoid water scarcity.

⁵ E.g., optimal, infeasible (i.e., no values could be found that satisfy all constraints in the model; this indicates that the input parameter values should be reconsidered), unbounded (i.e., no best value can be found, there is always a better solution satisfying all constraints).

Figure 16 - Example of result output from optimisation tool showing values for circularity indicators over the optimisation horizon

5 Examples

5.1 Introduction

In this section, we take semi-hypothetical examples using common elements from all WIDER UPTAKE case studies. This ensures that the demonstration remains relevant to all partners and covers certain aspects of each case study.

5.2 Circularity assessment example

5.2.1 Case study description

This is a semi-hypothetical case study demonstrating the circularity assessment for wastewater reuse in irrigation. The base line alternative is to use water for irrigation from the river. It is assumed that $6 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$ of water is diverted from a nearby river. 20% of the water seeps into the ground and 20% is assimilated by the crops. The resource recovery alternative is to recycle the effluent from the existing WWTP as a supplement for irrigation after additional UV treatment. The added UV treatment step uses $1.5 \times 10^4 \text{ kWh}/\text{y}$ energy to disinfect the wastewater before agricultural irrigation. Furthermore, in the reuse case, we assume that $1 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$ of the irrigation runoff is collected and reused as irrigation water. The analysed system is depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 17 – (a) The base line alternative of using river water for irrigation (b) An existing WWTP with an added UV treatment for obtaining irrigation water (resource application process).

5.2.2 Circularity assessment of resource application

Base line case

In the base line case, $6 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$ of irrigation water is diverted from a nearby river. River extraction is a form of virgin extraction of water and thus, all of the inflow is characterized as virgin extraction. After irrigation, we assume 20% of the irrigation water discharges into the ground and replenishes groundwater storage. Also, we assume that 20% of the irrigation water is assimilated into crops and thus, the total unrecovered water is $3.6 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^3/\text{y}$. These inputs are shown in Figure 18.

base line			
Resource category	Unit	Value	
Abiotic or mixed resources			
Biotic resources			
Water			
Total water	m ³ /y		60000
Fraction of water obtained from WWTP (F _{WWTP})	Fraction		0
Fraction of water reused within the same process (F _U)	Fraction		0
Fraction of water originating from another application process (F _R)	Fraction		0
Fraction of water going to a WWTP after use (C _{WWTP})	Fraction		0
Fraction of water reused within the same application process (C _U)	Fraction		0
Fraction of water going into another use process (C _R)	Fraction		0
Fraction of water discharged with a quality suitable to the receiving body (C _D)	Fraction		0.2
Fraction of water biologically assimilated (C _{BA})	Fraction		0.2
Total virgin mass	kg		60000
Total unrecovered waste mass	kg		36000

Figure 18 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool circularity assessment input sheet. The input data belongs to the base line case of using river water for irrigation.

Reuse case

A total of 6×10^5 m³/y of water is treated in the WWTP, out of which 3×10^4 m³/y of the effluent is UV treated and used for irrigation. Furthermore, 1×10^4 m³/y of the irrigation runoff water is collected and stored for use as irrigation water. The remaining required water for irrigation is obtained from the river as in the base line case. Since we wish to calculate the circularity of the irrigation process (resource application), the relevant total water quantity is the water required for irrigation, which is 6×10^4 m³/y. But now, 50% of the irrigation water is obtained from the WWTP and 16% from the collected runoff. After irrigation, 16% of the water is collected as runoff, 20% gets discharged to groundwater storage and 20% assimilated into crops. The total virgin water flow is 2.04×10^4 m³/y and the total unrecovered water flow is 2.64×10^4 m³/y, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Alternative 1			
Resource category	Unit	Value	
Abiotic or mixed resources			
Biotic resources			
Water			
Total water			60000
Fraction of water obtained from WWTP (F _{WWTP})	Fraction		0.5
Fraction of water reused within the same process (F _U)	Fraction		0.16
Fraction of water originating from another application process (F _R)	Fraction		0
Fraction of water going to a WWTP after use (C _{WWTP})	Fraction		0
Fraction of water reused within the same application process (C _U)	Fraction		0.16
Fraction of water going into another use process (C _R)	Fraction		0
Fraction of water discharged with a quality suitable to the receiving body (C _D)	Fraction		0.2
Fraction of water biologically assimilated (C _{BA})	Fraction		0.2
Total virgin mass	kg		20400
Total unrecovered waste mass	kg		26400

Figure 19 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool circularity assessment input sheet. The input data belongs to alternative 1 (resource recovery case) of using WWTP effluent for irrigation and recycling or irrigation runoff.

Result

Using the MCI method, the water circularity indicators for the base line and alternative 1 (water reuse case) are shown in Figure 20. The base line case of using river water for irrigation has a circularity value of 0.20 whereas, the alternative case shows an improvement of circularity to 0.61.

Figure 20 - Output of circularity assessment of the river water irrigation (base line) and WWTP effluent recycling case with reuse of irrigation runoff (alternative 1). Using the effluent for irrigation and collecting runoff improves circularity from 0.20 to 0.61.

Conclusion

The water reuse alternative is more circular due to a higher fraction of water being obtained from a WWTP, reducing dependence on river water diversion. Also, the reuse of irrigation runoff means that some of the water that would have been an unrecovered waste is now recovered and put to use again. Due to these factors, the irrigation process involving reuse water is 61% circular whereas the base line alternative of using river water for irrigation was only 20% circular.

5.3 Efficiency assessment example

5.3.1 Case study description

This is a semi-hypothetical case study related to calcite recovery from a water softening process. Calcite recovered from the softener is used for the production of a new bio-composite material which is, in turn, used to manufacture the riverbank protection elements used by a water company.

Calcium Carbonate (CaCO_3), commonly known as calcite, is often used in the drinking water softening process. The softening process consists of an upward-flow cylinder partly filled with calcite. Caustic soda is added to the hard water to raise its pH. This leads to a super-saturated condition in the water for calcium carbonate. As a result, calcium carbonate from hard water crystallizes around the existing calcite (Schetters et al., 2015). Only a part of the calcite produced by the softening reactors needs to be reused as seeding material; the rest is available as raw material for bio-composites. Below, we show how efficiency can be assessed for this resource recovery process. For this demonstration, we calculate two kinds of efficiencies. This case study is schematically depicted in Figure 21.

Figure 21 - (a) shows the base line water softening process wherein calcite is a by-product that is considered waste whereas, (b) shows the resource recovery case, wherein calcite is used for bio-composite manufacturing for canal bank protection.

5.3.2 Efficiency assessment of resource recovery

Below, we compare the efficiency of the base line water softening process without calcite recovery and the softening process with calcite being recovered for manufacturing bio-composites. We use two sets of efficiency indicators: service unit (SU)- based indicators and simple efficiencies (ratio of output to input energy/material resources/money).

In the base line softening process, 6×10^7 m³/y of water is treated. 7034 t/y of sodium hydroxide is used to cause the crystallization of calcite. A total of 5252 t/y of calcite is produced from this crystallization, out of which, 535 t/y is reused within the softening process as seed material. The remaining 4717 t/y calcite by-product is considered waste. The energy consumption of this softening process is assumed to be 7.1×10^5 kWh/y. The total operational and maintenance costs are assumed as 2000 €/y whereas annualized capital costs over the lifetime of the softener are assumed to be 3000 €/y. We assume that the softening process generates 1500 €/y as revenue as a result of producing soft water. The input values are shown in Figure 22.

5			Base line
6	Service unit (SU)	m ³ /y	60000000
7	Auxiliary service unit 1 (ASU-1)		
8	Auxiliary service unit 2 (ASU-2)		
9	Annual flows	Unit	Value
10	Material resource input rate (MIR)	t/y	7034
11	Waste output rate (WOR)	t/y	4717
12	Material resource output rate (MOR)	t/y	535
13	Energy input rate (EIR)	kWh/y	710000
14	Energy output rate (EOR)	kWh/y	0
15	Financial input rate (FIR)	€/y	5000
16	Financial output rate (FOR)	€/y	1500

Figure 22 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's efficiency assessment input sheet for the base line case.

In the calcite recovery alternative, this residual calcite is used for bio-composite manufacturing. Since calcite is no longer a residual flow but is used as raw material for manufacturing bio-composites, the total material resource output is now 5252 t/y. Due to the increased costs for collecting, treating, and transporting the calcite, we assume the annualized capital and operational costs have increased to 5000 €/y and 3000 €/y respectively. On the other hand, sale of the calcite generates extra income which takes the total revenue for the treatment facility up to 2000 €/y. For the resource recovery case, input data for efficiency assessment are shown in Figure 23.

5			Alternative 1
6	Service unit (SU)	m ³ /y	60000000
7	Auxiliary service unit 1 (ASU-1)		
8	Auxiliary service unit 2 (ASU-2)		
9	Annual flows	Unit	Value
10	Material resource input rate (MIR)	t/y	7034
11	Waste output rate (WOR)	t/y	0
12	Material resource output rate (MOR)	t/y	5252
13	Energy input rate (EIR)	kWh/y	710000
14	Energy output rate (EOR)	kWh/y	0
15	Financial input rate (FIR)	€/y	8000
16	Financial output rate (FOR)	€/y	2000

Figure 23 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's efficiency assessment input sheet for alternative 1 (calcite recovery case).

Result

The results of the efficiency assessment of the two options are shown here. For the base line case, service unit-material efficiency is 8530 m³/kg and, its service unit-financial efficiency is 12 000 m³/€ (see Figure 24 Figure 25).

3	Resource recovery process		
4	Service unit efficiency	Unit	Base line
5	Service unit-material efficiency (SU-mat)	m ³ /y / t/y	8530.00
7	Service unit-financial efficeincy (SU-fin)	m ³ /y / €/y	12000.00

Figure 24 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's efficiency assessment output sheet for base line case. The efficiency values show service unit-based material and financial efficiencies.

The simple material and financial efficiency values for the base line case, as shown in Figure 25, are 0.08 and 0.30 respectively.

22	Simple efficiency (output/input)	Unit	Base line
23	Material efficiency	-	0.08
25	Financial efficiency	-	0.30

Figure 25 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's efficiency assessment output sheet for base line case. The simple efficiency values are shown.

The service unit-material efficiency for alternative 1 (calcite recovery case) remains the same as the base line case at 8530 m³/kg. However, the service unit-financial efficiency is seen to have a lower value of 7500 m³/€ (see Figure 26).

3	Resource recovery process		
4	Service unit efficiency	Unit	Alternative 1
5	Service unit-material efficiency (SU-mat)	m ³ /y / t/y	8530.00
7	Service unit-financial efficeincy (SU-fin)	m ³ /y / €/y	7500.00

Figure 26 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's efficiency assessment output sheet for alternative 1 (calcite recovery case). The efficiency values show service unit-based material and financial efficiencies.

The simple material and financial efficiency values for alternative 1 (calcite recovery case) are shown in Figure 27 as 0.75 and 0.25 respectively.

22	Simple efficiency (output/input)	Unit	Alternative 1
23	Material efficiency	-	0.75
25	Financial efficiency	-	0.25

Figure 27- Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's efficiency assessment output sheet for alternative 1 (calcite recovery case). The simple efficiency values are shown.

Conclusion

We compared a resource recovery alternative to a base line water softening process. Both the base line and the resource recovery alternative have the same resource input so there was no difference in their service unit material resource efficiencies. However, resource recovery led to a lower fraction of calcite that ends up as unrecovered waste. This caused a significant improvement in material efficiency (ratio of resource output to resource input) from 0.08 to 0.75, an increase of 838%. Collecting, treating, and transporting calcite for its subsequent use added to the capital and operational costs of the treatment plant. Selling calcite also led to increased revenue. The service unit financial efficiency of the softener is reduced from 12 000 m³/€ to 7500 m³/€, a reduction of 37.5%. Also, financial efficiency (ratio of revenue to investment) drops from 0.30 to 0.25, a reduction of 17%. This shows how improved material efficiency may come at the cost of reduced financial efficiency.

5.4 Multi-criteria Decision Analysis

5.4.1 Case study description

This example ranks two alternatives shown in the calcite recovery case study in Section 5.3.2 by using MCDA. A total of four indicators were used to assess these two alternatives in the section above. With respect to SU-material efficiency, both options have the same value, for simple material efficiency, the calcite recovery alternative performs better, whereas the base line alternative proves more financially efficient. To select the optimal alternative, an MCDA method needs to be applied. Since an MCDA method helps to account for different perspectives, the optimal solution in this example is likely to vary based on the weights attached to financial and material efficiencies. Thus, we conduct an MCDA using the three indicators that show different values for the two options.

5.4.2 MCDA-based Ranking

Here, we show compromise programming MCDA on the example from Section 4.3.2. We compare the two alternatives (base line and calcite recovery) on their performance in terms of simple efficiency and service unit-based efficiency for two different sets of weights.

Two sets of weights for the criteria are used here. In the first instance, we use equal weighting for the three criteria (i.e., 0.33 each) as shown in Figure 28. The second time, we give a lower weight to the financial efficiency indicators as shown in Figure 29.

Resource recovery process				CP Distance	Rank
Criteria	Efficiency				
Indicators	SU-financial efficiency	Simple material efficiency	Simple financial efficiency		
Units	m ³ /kg		-		
User weights	0.33	0.33	0.33		
Minimisation?	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE		
Normalisation minimum	12000.00	0.00	0.00		
Normalisation maximum	7500.00	1.00	1.00		
Base line	12000.00	0.08	0.30	0.385	1
Alternative 1	7500.00	0.75	0.25	0.425	2

Figure 28 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's MCDA sheet shows three indicator values for the base line and alternative 1 (resource recovery case) and the indicator weighting on the left side. On the right side, the CP distance for the two options and their ranks are shown. The base line option is ranked 1 because of its shorter CP distance of 0.385.

Input data				Results		
Resource recovery process						
Indicators	Criteria	Efficiency			CP Distance	Rank
		SU-financial efficiency	Simple material efficiency	Simple financial efficiency		
Units		m ³ /kg		-		
User weights		0.20	0.60	0.20		
Minimisation?		FALSE	FALSE	FALSE		
Normalisation minimum		12000.00	0.00	0.00		
Normalisation maximum		7500.00	1.00	1.00		
	Base line	12000.00	0.08	0.30	0.569	2
	Alternative 1	7500.00	0.75	0.25	0.292	1

Figure 29 - Screenshot from the spreadsheet tool's MCDA sheet shows three indicator values for the base line and alternative 1 (resource recovery case) and the indicator weighting on the left side. On the right side, the CP distance for the two options and their ranks are shown. Alternative 1 is ranked 1 because of its shorter CP distance of 0.292.

Conclusion

The CP-MCDA method allows users to choose the optimal option among two or more alternatives. The optimal option is one that is at the shortest distance from a theoretical ideal point. In the above example, when equal weights are assigned to the three criteria, the base line alternative is found to be closer to the ideal solution. On the contrary, when financial efficiencies are given lower weights, the calcite recovery alternative proves to be better. In this manner, the CP method can account for different stakeholder perspectives in decision-making.

6 Summary and conclusions

An efficiency and circularity assessment, and optimisation framework was developed. The framework is meant to be applied to symbiotic circular economy solutions in the water sector. The assessment methods help to estimate the circularity and the different kinds of efficiencies (material, energy, service unit-based, etc.) of SCES, whereas the optimisation part covers multi-criteria decision analysis and mathematical optimisation approaches that help to make decisions, accommodating multiple criteria and different stakeholder perspectives.

The relevant concepts, such as circular economy and efficiency, were first described. Next, resources commonly recovered from water were classified into four categories: abiotic or mixed, biotic, water and nutrients. Thereafter, the assessment methods were explained along with small examples to aid understanding. For circularity assessment, the material circularity indicator method was introduced. The scope of this method was adapted to fit the resource categories created earlier. Based on biogeochemical cycle models of N, P, and water, linear and restorative/regenerative flows were described. Based on these two sets of flows, equations to calculate circularity for the resource categories were developed. Thus, through this method, the circularity of a particular resource recovery or application process with respect to abiotic resources, biotic resources, water, and nutrients can be assessed. The circularity value can lie between 0 and 1 representing a completely linear and a completely circular system, respectively. The circularity scores can be used to compare two different RR or RA processes, or to estimate the circularity improvement of a single process. A high circularity value for a process implies that a significant portion of the material resource

flowing through the process can be considered restorative/regenerative. Measuring circularity improvement in this manner helps to quantify the extent to which virgin extraction and unrecovered wastes have been minimized through the development of an SCES. This, in turn, helps to reduce resource intensity and waste generation of not only the water sector, but also other sectors that are symbiotically linked. This can potentially lead to improved material, energy, and financial resource efficiency of multiple sectors linked symbiotically.

Efficiency was defined as the ratio between benefits and costs of an SCES. Cost indicators were discussed at the level of resource flows and the environmental impacts of those flows, captured by a life cycle impact assessment. Benefit indicators included the categories of resource outputs, service units, and auxiliary service units. Combining these cost and benefit indicators leads to three sets of three efficiency indicators. Simple efficiency was described as the ratio of output to input resource flow rates (material, energy, or financial); service unit-based efficiencies were introduced as the ratio of the main service unit of a process to the input resource flow rates (material, energy or financial), and lastly, auxiliary service unit-based indicators were explained to be the ratio of an auxiliary service unit of a process to input resource flow rates (material, energy or financial).

The simple efficiency indicators indicate the extent to which resources may be dissipated while flowing through a particular process. A lower simple efficiency value signifies that a larger portion of the value of input resources (material/energy/financial) is dissipated by a process and is consequently lost. A higher simple efficiency value suggests that a greater portion of input resource value is maintained by a process and available for recovery. Thus, a higher simple efficiency implies a more efficient process that conserves resource value.

Every process can be attributed with one main and possibly several auxiliary services that it provides for human society (benefit) and with resources that it consumes (costs). The service unit and auxiliary service unit-based indicators provide an estimate for how higher efficiency in the water sector can lead to a larger population served at lower resource cost.

Next, optimisation methods were explained. First, the MCDA method was introduced along with an example. The MCDA method employed in this framework is called compromise programming. In CP, a user identifies an imaginary ideal solution for which all criteria achieve their optimal values. The distance between the actual alternatives and the imaginary alternatives is used to rank the alternatives. The alternative closest to the ideal solution is ranked the highest. Different weights can be assigned to the various criteria, thus taking into account, various stakeholder perspectives.

The subsequent section presented an approach based on mathematical optimisation. It has a value-chain perspective on industrial symbiosis, suggesting ways to coordinate activities between the various involved entities. The aim is to identify relations (resource flows) between the entities and best suited transformation processes to achieve efficient resource usage and increased circularity. The focus is on treatment of incoming wastewater, extraction of valuable resources, and processing them such that they offer more environmentally friendly and socially favourable alternatives to currently used products. The approach was explained in general terms, an optimisation model was formulated and its implementation as a software tool was outlined. Further, it was discussed how the approach is placed in the WIDER UPTAKE project landscape.

Lastly, the methods were demonstrated on semi-hypothetical examples of WIDER UPTAKE SCES. The case studies included water reuse for irrigation and calcite recovery for bio-composite manufacturing. The examples showed how water circularity improves by shifting from river water to WWTP effluent for irrigation. Also, the example displayed the

circularity improvement of reusing irrigation runoff. The second example showed how the efficiency of a water softening process is improved when residual calcite output is collected for manufacturing bio-composites. However, this example points towards the importance of having a wide range of efficiency indicators since even though material efficiency saw an improvement, the financial efficiency was found to be lowered for the calcite recovery case. In the presence of several criteria and different perspectives of decision-makers, it was shown how the CP-MCDA method can be helpful. It was shown how any number of criteria and indicators may be included in the decision-making process. Furthermore, it was demonstrated how changing weights of the criteria can lead to different alternatives to be optimal.

To conclude, this framework is a useful tool for decision-makers to assess the efficiency and circularity of SCES. It allows users to select relevant indicators belonging to the criteria of efficiency and circularity, assess a given SCES, and optimise the decision-making process.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Calculating Material Circularity Indicator (MCI)

In this section, we derive equations to calculate the material circularity indicators for four resource categories defined in the report: Abiotic/mixed, biotic, nutrients, and water.

Abiotic/mixed resources

1. *Virgin material used*

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U)$$

where V is the virgin feedstock, F_R is the fraction of feedstock derived from recycled sources, and F_U is the fraction of feedstock derived from reused sources.

2. *Unrecoverable waste*

$$W = M(1 - C_R - C_U)$$

where W is the unrecovered waste, C_R is the fraction of the resource being collected for recycling after use, and C_U is the fraction of the resource going into component reuse.

3. *Linear Flow Indicator (LFI)*

$$LFI = \frac{V + W}{2M}$$

where, LFI is the linear flow indicator, and M is the total quantity (mass or volume) of a particular resource flowing through a process.

4. *Abiotic material circularity indicator*

$$AMCI = 1 - LFI$$

where $AMCI$ is the abiotic or mixed material circularity indicator.

Biotic resources

1. *Virgin material used*

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U - F_S)$$

where V is the virgin feedstock, M is the total quantity (mass or volume) of a resource flowing through a process, F_R is the fraction of feedstock derived from recycled sources, F_U is the fraction of feedstock derived from reused sources, F_S is the fraction of biological material from sustained production (such that regeneration > appropriation).

2. *Unrecoverable waste*

$$W = M(1 - C_R - C_U - C_C)$$

where W is the unrecovered waste, C_R is the fraction of the resource being collected for recycling after use, C_U is the fraction of the resource going into component reuse, and C_C is the fraction of the resource comprising uncontaminated biological materials that is composted.

3. *Linear Flow Indicator (LFI)*

$$LFI = \frac{V+W}{2M}$$

where LFI is the linear flow indicator for biotic resources.

4. *Biotic material circularity indicator (BMCI)*

$$BMCI = 1 - LFI$$

where *BMCI* is the biotic material circularity indicator.

Nutrients

Nitrogen

In terms of Nitrogen, virgin extraction refers to converting unreactive N_2 gas into reactive species using the Haber Bosch or any other industrial process. We consider any N incorporated into biomass or returned to the atmosphere as N_2 to be restorative flows. Whereas N losses, such as Nitrate leaching, volatilization, etc. are linear flows.

1. Virgin material used

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U)$$

where V is the virgin N feedstock, M is the total quantity (mass or volume) of N flowing through a process, F_R is the fraction of N recycled from sources such as wastewater, and F_U is the fraction of N internally recycled within a process such as internal recycling within agricultural soil.

2. Unrecoverable waste

$$W = M(1 - C_{imm} - C_S - C_P - C_{UR})$$

where M is the total mass of N used in a process, C_{imm} represents the fraction of N assimilated by microorganisms, C_S is the fraction of N fixed into the soil, C_P is the fraction of N taken up by plants, C_{UR} is the fraction of N returned to the atmosphere as N_2 .

3. Linear Flow Indicator

$$LFI = \frac{V + W}{2M}$$

where LFI is the linear flow indicator for N .

4. Nitrogen circularity indicator

$$NCI = 1 - LFI$$

where NCI is the nitrogen circularity indicator.

Phosphorus

1. Virgin material used

$$V = M(1 - F_R - F_U)$$

where F_R is the fraction of phosphorus recycled from secondary sources such as wastewater, F_U is the fraction of phosphorus internally recycled.

2. Unrecoverable waste

$$W = M(1 - C_{imm} - C_S - C_P)$$

where M is the total mass of P used in an application, C_{imm} represents the fraction of P assimilated by microorganisms, C_S represents the fraction of P fixed into the soil, and C_P is the fraction of P taken up by plants.

Water

1. Virgin extraction

$$V = M(1 - F_{WWTP} - F_U - F_R)$$

where V is the total virgin water quantity, M is the total quantity of water flowing through a process, F_{WWTP} is the fraction of water mass that originates from a wastewater treatment plant, F_U is the fraction of water mass recirculated within the same application process, and F_R is the fraction of water mass that originates from another application process.

2. *Unrecoverable waste*

$$W = M(1 - C_{WWTP} - C_U - C_R - C_D)$$

where W is the unrecovered waste water, M is the total quantity of water flowing through a process, C_{WWTP} is the fraction of water mass being diverted to a treatment plant, C_U is the fraction of water mass recirculated within the same process, C_R is the fraction of water mass diverted for another application and C_D is the fraction of water mass being discharged into nature after reuse.

3. *Linear Flow Indicator*

$$LFI = \frac{V + W}{2M}$$

where LFI is the linear flow indicator for water.

4. *Water Circularity Indicator*

$$WCI = 1 - LFI$$

where WCI is the water circularity indicator.

8.1 List of objectives, criteria, and indicators

The following Table 3 shows a list of objectives, criteria, and indicators to be used for efficiency assessment of SCES.

Table 3 - A sample of objectives, criteria, and indicators to be used for circularity and efficiency assessment of SCES.

Objective	Criteria	Indicators	Indicator description
To reduce resource extraction and waste assimilation pressure on natural environment.	Circularity	MCI (calculation explained in previous section)	Material circularity indicator (MCI) calculated as fraction of total flow that is not linear (i.e., originates from virgin extraction and/or that ends at landfills, incineration, etc.).
To provide benefits to human society in the form of useful outflows of materials, energy, money, services, or desirable attributes of the resources / services.	Material resource benefit	Material resource output rate (MOR) in kg/y or m ³ /y	MOR is the annual rate of resource recovery.
	Energy benefit	Energy output rate (EOR) in kWh/y	EOR is the annual rate of energy recovered from a process.
	Financial benefit	Financial output rate (FOR) in €/y	FOR is the annual revenue generated by a process.
	Health & environmental benefit	$EQ = WQP_{influent} - WQP_{effluent}$	Effluent quality (EQ) improvement measured in difference between

			water quality parameters (WQP) such as BOD, total N, among others between influent and effluent.
	Service unit benefit (specific to case studies)	Q_{water} in m^3/y	Q_{water} is the quantity of water treated at a drinking water or wastewater plant per year.
		Annual crop yield (ACY) in kg/y	ACY is the annual crop yield from using reuse water for irrigation or using recovered nutrients as fertilizers.
To gain maximum benefits to human society with minimum input of resources, and minimum environmental impact.	Material resource cost	Material resource input rate (MIR) in kg/y	MIR is the annual rate of resource input to a process.
		Waste output rate (WOR) in kg/y	WOR is the annual rate of waste output of a process.
To gain maximum benefits to human society with minimum input of resources, and minimum environmental impact.	Energy resource cost	Energy input rate (EIR) in kWh/y	EIR is the annual rate of energy used by a process.
	Financial cost	Financial input rate (FIR) in $\text{€}/\text{y}$	FIR is the annualized monetary investment to run a process.
	Environmental impact cost		LCIA is the life cycle impact assessment result for an environmental damage category 'i', calculated using LCA, w_i is the weight of this category.

8.2 Some relevant environmental impact categories

Since the relevant environmental impacts would differ from case to case, the categories discussed here does not reflect a comprehensive list. The relevant categories will be selected when dealing with the individual case studies in the WIDER UPTAKE project.

Global warming

Among the emissions responsible for the green-house effect, CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O are the ones relevant to a water treatment plant (Bani Shahabadi et al., 2010; Hao et al., 2019).

Eutrophication

The main contributors towards eutrophication impacts of a WWTP are Nitrogen (N) and Phosphorus (P) (Hao et al., 2019; Zang et al., 2015). Eutrophication should be treated separately under the categories of freshwater and marine eutrophication caused by P and N respectively (Goedkoop & Huijbregts, 2013).

Toxicity

Most LCA studies on water treatment plants are limited to considering toxicity impacts of heavy metals (Zang et al., 2015).

Acidification

The main emissions causing acidification are nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ammonia (NH₃), and sulphur dioxide (SO₂).

Photochemical oxidant potential

Ozone formation can take place due to emissions of NO_x and CO (Zang et al., 2015).

Ozone depletion

Depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer can be attributed mainly to emissions of fluorine, bromine, chlorine, etc. (Zang et al., 2015).

A characterization factor table (see Table 4) is included in this framework for easy calculation of the above explained impacts in case a full LCA is not possible. This table only shows a sample of emissions and their characterization factors. The complete table is available in Huijbregts et al. (2016).

Table 4: A sample of Impact categories, main emissions, and their characterization factors to be used for a non-comprehensive LCA as part of the efficiency assessment of SCES.

Impact categories	Main emissions	Compartment	Characterization factors
Global warming (GWP100), (kgCO₂ eq.)	CO ₂	Air	1
	CH ₄	Air	34
	N ₂ O	Air	298
Marine eutrophication (kg N-eq to marine water/kg)	N	Freshwater	0.30
		Agricultural soil	0.13
		Seawater	1
	NH ₄ ⁺	Freshwater	0.23
		Agricultural soil	0.10
		Seawater	0.78
	NH ₃	Freshwater	0.24
		Agricultural soil	0.10
		Seawater	0.82
	NO	Freshwater	0.14
		Agricultural soil	0.06
		Seawater	0.47
	NO ₂	Freshwater	0.09
		Agricultural soil	0.04
		Seawater	0.30
NO ₃	Freshwater	0.07	

		Agricultural soil	0.03
		Seawater	0.23
	NO _x	Freshwater	0.09
		Agricultural soil	0.04
		Seawater	0.30
Freshwater eutrophication (kg P-eq to freshwater/kg)	Phosphorus (P)	Freshwater	1
		Agricultural soil	0.1
		Seawater	0
	Phosphate (PO ₄ ³⁻)	Freshwater	0.33
		Agricultural soil	0.033
		Seawater	0
	Phosphoric acid	Freshwater	0.32
		Agricultural soil	0.032
		Seawater	0
	Phosphorus pentoxide	Freshwater	0.22
Agricultural soil		0.022	
Seawater		0	
Terrestrial acidification (kg SO₂-eq/kg)	SO ₂	-	1.00
	NH ₃	-	1.96
	NO _x	-	0.36
Ozone depletion (kg CFC11-eq/kg)	CFC11	-	1
	CFC12	-	0.421
	CFC113	-	0.504
	CFC114	-	0.165
	CFC115	-	0.032
	Halon-1301	-	11.841
	Halon-1211	-	15.053
	Halon-2402	-	22.2
	CCl ₄	-	1.203
	CH ₃ CCl ₃	-	0.396
	CH ₃ Br	-	1.649
	Halon-1202	-	4.247
	Land occupation	Occupation, pasture, manmade, intensive	-
Occupation, permanent crop, irrigated, intensive		-	0.7